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Potential anticonvulsant drugs—Part II.

Synthesis of Succinimido/Phthalimido Butyryl Ureas and Thioureas

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DECREASE in the availability of γ -aminobutyric acid (GABA) in the central nervous system has been established¹⁻³ to be one of the reasons behind convulsive disorders. α -Ethyl- α -methyl succinimido is reported to be effective⁴⁻⁵ as an anticonvulsant agent. Phenyl urea derivatives have also been shown to possess significant anticonvulsant properties⁶⁻¹⁴.

On the basis of these observations a number of *N*-(γ -succinimido/ γ -phthalimido)-butyryl-*N'*-aryl ureas and thioureas have been designed. In the present communication synthesis of these compounds and their efficacy as anticonvulsants are reported.

γ -Phthalimido butyric acid, γ -phthalimido butyryl chloride and aryl ureas were obtained by procedures described in the literature¹⁵⁻¹⁷.

(a) γ -Succinimido butyric acid

Succinic anhydride (10 g, 0.01 mole) and γ -amino-butyric acid (10.3 g, 0.01 mole) were fused for 30 mins. at 120° in an oil bath. The crude product obtained on cooling was recrystallised from benzene, m.p. 90°. Yield 14.8 g (80%). Anal. calculated for C, H and N: C, 51.89%; H, 5.94; N, 7.53. Found: C, 52.4%; H, 5.45; N, 7.44. I.R. C-N: 3250 cm⁻¹; C=O: 1680 cm⁻¹ C=O: 1760 cm⁻¹.

(b) γ -Succinimido butyryl chloride:

In a two necked flask equipped with a reflux condenser a guard tube, and a dropping funnel, were placed γ -succinimido butyric acid (9.25 g.) and dry chloroform (40 ml.). Thionyl chloride (6.5 g) was slowly added with occasional stirring. The reaction mixture was then warmed on a water bath for 4 hrs. The excess of thionyl chloride and chloroform were removed under reduced pressure. The solid product thus obtained was used for further reactions without purification.

(c) *N*-(γ -succinimido/ γ -phthalimido)-butyryl-*N'*-Aryl ureas:

A mixture of (γ -succinimido/ γ -phthalimido)-butyryl chloride (0.001 mole), dry chloroform/benzene (10 ml), and appropriate aryl ureas was refluxed on a steam bath for 6-7 hrs. At the end of this period the solvent was removed under reduced pressure, residue extracted with water and recrystallised from ethanol.

The analysis, m.p. and other data are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

Sl. No.	R	R ¹	M.P. °C	Molecular formula	% N	
					Calcd.	Found
1.	Succinimido	H	185	C ₁₅ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₄	13.86	13.45
2.	"	<i>o</i> -CH ₃	205	C ₁₆ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₄	13.25	12.94
3.	"	<i>m</i> -CH ₃	210	C ₁₆ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₄	13.25	13.02
4.	"	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	216	C ₁₆ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₄	13.25	12.99
5.	"	<i>o</i> -OCH ₃	225	C ₁₆ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₅	12.61	12.12
6.	"	<i>m</i> -OCH ₃	235	C ₁₆ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₅	12.61	12.04
7.	"	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃	240	C ₁₆ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₅	12.61	12.26
8.	"	<i>p</i> -Cl	185	C ₁₅ H ₁₆ N ₃ O ₄ Cl	12.42	12.32
9.	Phthalimido	H	218	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₄	11.96	11.89
10.	"	<i>o</i> -CH ₃	230	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₄	11.83	11.80
11.	"	<i>m</i> -CH ₃	175	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₄	11.83	11.78
12.	"	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	210	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₄	11.83	11.74
13.	"	<i>o</i> -OCH ₃	261	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₅	11.02	10.98
14.	"	<i>m</i> -OCH ₃	280	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₅	11.02	10.94
15.	"	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃	270	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₅	11.02	10.96
16.	"	<i>p</i> -Cl	194	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ N ₃ O ₄ Cl	10.86	10.76

(a) All the melting points were taken in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected.

(b) These compounds were obtained in 65-75% yields.

N-(γ -succinimido/ γ -phthalimido)-butyryl-*N'*-aryl thioureas :

(γ -succinimido/ γ -phthalimido)-butyryl chloride (0.002 mole) was taken in dry acetone in a three necked flask equipped with a reflux condenser, a dropping funnel and a mechanical stirrer. Ammonium thiocyanate (0.002 mole) in dry acetone (10 ml) was introduced dropwise to the above solution under constant stirring. The mixture was then warmed for 30 mins. The appropriate arylamine (0.002 moles) in dry acetone was next introduced dropwise and the solution further warmed for 45 mins. The contents of the flask were then poured carefully on crushed ice and recrystallised from ethanol.

The analysis, m.p. and other data are recorded in Table 2.

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TABLE 2

Sl. No.	R	R'	M.P. °C	Molecular formula	% N	
					Calcd.	Found
$\text{R}-\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}_2-\text{CO}-\text{NH}-\text{CS}-\text{NH}-\langle \text{O} \rangle-\text{R}'$						
1.	Succinimido	H	152	C ₁₅ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₃ S	13.16	12.63
2.	"	<i>o</i> -CH ₃	155	C ₁₆ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₃ S	12.61	12.44
3.	"	<i>m</i> -CH ₃	148	C ₁₆ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₃ S	12.61	12.36
4.	"	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	134	C ₁₆ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₃ S	12.61	12.52
5.	"	<i>o</i> -OCH ₃	166	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ N ₃ O ₄ S	12.03	11.92
6.	"	<i>m</i> -OCH ₃	172	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ N ₃ O ₄ S	12.03	11.88
7.	"	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃	161	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ N ₃ O ₄ S	12.03	11.74
8.	"	<i>p</i> -Cl	144	C ₁₅ H ₁₆ N ₃ O ₃ S Cl	11.86cl	11.38
9.	Phthalimido	H	174	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ N ₃ O ₃ S	11.44	11.24
10.	"	<i>o</i> -CH ₃	160	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₃ S	11.02	10.76
11.	"	<i>m</i> -CH ₃	165	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₃ S	11.02	10.84
12.	"	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	170	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₃ S	11.02	10.69
13.	"	<i>o</i> -OCH ₃	185	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ N ₃ O ₄ S	10.58	10.24
14.	"	<i>m</i> -OCH ₃	189	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ N ₃ O ₄ S	10.58	10.44
15.	"	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃	180	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ N ₃ O ₄ S	10.58	10.38
16.	"	<i>p</i> -Cl	170	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ N ₃ O ₃ Cl	10.44	9.98

V. R = Succinimido
VI. R = Phthalimido

Bioassay

The anticonvulsant properties of compound nos. 1, 2, 3, 9, 10, 11 (Table 1) and 1, 2, 3, 9, 10, 11 (Table 2) were determined against pentylenetetrazole induced convulsions in mice. Urea derivatives specially those derived from succinimides showed good anticonvulsant effects whereas thiourea derivatives were devoid of significant anticonvulsant activity. *N*- γ -succinimido-butyl-*N'*-*m*-tolyl urea was the most active compound of this series. A LD₅₀ of these compounds ranged from 750 to 1000 mg/kg.

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